

A new method of synthesis and characterization of nano-sized mercuric iodide by solid-gas reaction

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Abstract : Nano-sized crystalline mercuric iodide with space group $P4_2/nmc$ has been synthesized in the solid-state by reaction between mercurous nitrate and iodine vapour using inexpensive glass capillary, microslide and specially designed glass channel for the first time. Kinetics of the reaction was studied by measuring weight (w) of sample as a function of time (t). It is found to increase linearly with time, obeying the equation $w = mt + c$, where m and c are slope and intercept respectively. In case of glass channel, thickness of the reaction product was noted as a function of time. The reaction product was characterized by powder X-ray diffraction studies, transmission electron microscopy (TEM) and diffuse reflectance spectroscopy (DRS). Nano-sized particles of mercuric iodide in the range 7–52 nm were obtained. Selected area electron diffraction (SAED) study also verified the nanocrystallinity of the product. It may be useful in imaging applications.

Keywords : Solid gas reaction, nano-sized mercuric iodide, kinetic studies, TEM.

Introduction

Solid state and material chemistry have played a significant role in the design and development of new functional materials in areas such as energy, catalysis and electronics¹.

Products from solid state reactions are always thermodynamically stable compounds. It is a solvent free reaction which allows the reactants to chemically react in the absence of any solvent.

The advantages of such type of reactions ripple throughout many industries. Since there is no solvent, there is no waste to eliminate at the end of the reaction. It will costless and is more environmentally friendly and comes under the green chemistry. Solid state reactions provide the study of synthesis, structure and properties of the solid phase materials which have commercial and industrial importance. The phenomenon of pattern formation^{2–12} is of current interest from the view point of many disciplines ranging from chemistry, physics, pharmaceuticals, material science, biology etc. Far from equilibrium net-

works of physico-chemical processes may exhibit structures in time, space or a combination of both⁶. Due to unusual physico-chemical properties compared to bulk counter parts, nanostructured materials have potential applications^{13–19} such as catalysts, drug delivery materials and photonic materials.

There has been intensive research interest to control over the size, shape and dimensionality of nanocrystals. Although, a number of techniques for the synthesis of nanomaterials are known but very little is known about its synthesis by solid gas reactions. Mercuric iodide is widely used in nuclear medicine, blister ointments, X-ray imaging systems and satellite based microchips for X- and gamma ray mapping. In the present paper, we report the synthesis and characterization of nanostructured mercuric iodide by solid gas reaction using inexpensive techniques for the first time.

Experimental

Materials : Mercurous nitrate (AR, CDH) and iodine (GR, S. Merck) were used as such.

Procedure :

In the present investigation, nano-sized mercuric iodide has been synthesized for the first time by solid gas reaction between mercurous nitrate and iodine using simple, inexpensive glass apparatuses and a specially designed glass channel. The products were characterized by powder X-ray diffraction, transmission electron microscopy and diffuse reflectance spectroscopic studies. Reaction between mercurous nitrate and iodine has been studied in the solid state using different experimental arrangements, (i) in a glass capillary, (ii) on the micro-slide and (iii) in a glass channel.

Reaction in a glass capillary :

Reaction between mercurous nitrate (s) and iodine was studied using an experimental set-up as shown in Fig. 1(a). It consists of a small conical flask fitted with a capillary with removable joint (inner diameter 2 mm). Iodine was put into the vessel. Mercurous nitrate was filled in the capillary having a standard joint. After joining the capillary with the vessel, the smooth surface of mercurous nitrate was exposed with iodine vapor. Experiments were performed in an air thermostat maintained at fixed temperature 35.0 ± 0.1 °C. The surface of mercurous nitrate was observed with a Nikon camera before the reaction started as well as after two and ten days. Photographs were taken and results are shown in Fig. 1(b).

Reaction on the micro slide :

The reaction on a micro-slide, mercurous nitrate was powdered and a thin film was prepared. It was pressed by another glass plate to make the surface uniform. The second plate was then removed and put in the iodine chamber as shown in Fig. 2(a). As soon the iodine vapour comes in contact with the surface, reaction starts. Experiment was performed in an incubator maintained at a fixed temperature 35.0 ± 0.1 °C.

Reaction in the glass channel :

Experiment was also performed in a specially designed glass-channel in which the solid reactant mercurous nitrate was put adjacent to iodine crystals as shown in Fig. 3(a). The channel was designed by taking a glass plate (A) (6 cm × 3.5 cm) and a glass channel (B) (7 cm × 2.5 cm) fixed above it. It contains a thin glass plate C (6 cm × 1 cm × 1 mm) which was put over the rectangular

Fig. 1. (a) Experimental setup to study the reaction between mercurous nitrate and iodine on the surface of a glass capillary. (b) Changes in the microscopic organization before, after 2 and 10 days respectively.

groove (6 cm × 1 mm). Solid mercurous nitrate (D) was put in the groove. Solid iodine crystals (E) were put at its interface. The channel was kept in the incubator maintained at a fixed temperature.

Diffuse reflectance spectral studies :

The product was also characterized by diffuse reflectance (DR) spectral studies using Shimadzu UV-2450 spectrophotometer. The base line was fixed using a barium sulphate reference. Results are shown in Fig. 4.

Fig. 2. (a) Experimental setup to study the reaction between mercurous nitrate and iodine vapour on a micro slide. (b) Plot between weight of material (w) versus time respectively at 35.0 ± 0.1 °C.

Powder X-ray diffraction studies :

The reaction product was characterized by powder X-ray diffraction (PXRD) studies in the 2θ range $0-70^\circ$ using Ni filtered $\text{CuK}\alpha$ ($\lambda = 1.54184 \text{ \AA}$) radiation. Normal scans were recorded with a step size of 0.02 \AA and step time of 1 s. Results are recorded in Fig. 5.

Transmission electron microscopic (TEM) studies :

Transmission electron microscopic (TEM) study was also carried out using Phillips transmission electron microscope (Model CM 200). Results are shown in Fig. 6.

Results and discussion

An orange-red reaction product was obtained by solid-gas reaction between mercurous nitrate and iodine vapour on the surface of a glass capillary, micro slide and specially designed glass channel as shown in Figs. 1–3. In case of a reaction on the surface of the glass capillary [Fig. 1(a)], initially the surface of mercurous nitrate was white but as soon as the iodine vapour comes in contact with the chemically reactive surface of solid mercurous nitrate, reaction starts and orange-red crystals appear on

Fig. 3. (a) Diagram of a glass channel to study the reaction between mercurous nitrate and iodine (A) glass plate, (B) glass channel, (C) moving thin glass plate, (D) thin film of mercurous nitrate, (E) iodine crystals and (F) orange-red reaction product at 35.0 ± 0.1 °C. (b) Plot of thickness of the reaction product (ζ) as a function of time at 35.0 ± 0.1 °C. (c) Close view of the orange-red product.

the surface which finally covers the entire surface in 10 days as shown in Fig. 1(b)(iii). The reaction is primarily propagating by vapour phase diffusion. The reaction on a micro slide was carried out using an experimental setup [Fig. 2(a)]. The kinetics of the reaction was monitored by

Fig. 4. Diffuse reflectance spectra of mercurous nitrate (a) and the reaction product (b).

measuring the weight of the sample on the micro slide at different time intervals. Results are shown in Fig. 2(b). Weight of the material (w) on the micro-slide was measured as a function of time (t). It increased with time linearly following the empirical equation $w = mt + c$ where m and c are slope and intercept respectively, as evident by a linear plot between w and t . Experiment was also performed in a specially designed glass channel [Fig. 3(a)]. The reaction takes place due to diffusion of iodine into solid mercurous nitrate to form an orange-red product. The kinetics of reaction was monitored by measuring the thickness (ζ) of the orange-red product (F) as the function of time. A sigmoid curve with an induction pe-

Fig. 5. (a-b) Powder X-ray diffraction patterns of mercurous nitrate and orange-red reaction product respectively.

Fig. 6. TEM images (a-c) and SAED pattern (d) of nano-sized crystalline mercuric iodide synthesized in the solid state.

riod was obtained as shown in Fig. 3(b). The microscopic view of the product formed is shown in Fig. 3(c).

The diffuse reflectance spectra of mercurous nitrate and the orange-red product are shown in Fig. 4. The spectrum of the reactant [Fig. 4(a)] was compared with that of the product [Fig. 4(b)]. Results showed that the product was different from that of the reactant as evident by a new broad peak in the photon energy region 2.166–2.332 eV.

Powder X-ray diffraction patterns of the reactant mercurous nitrate was compared with that of the product. Results are shown in Figs. 5(a) and 5(b) respectively. The reaction product was characterized as HgI₂ with the space group P4₂/nmc.

Transmission electron microscopic images (TEM) and selection area electron diffraction (SAED) pattern of the product are shown in Fig. 6. TEM results revealed the formation of disk-like nano-sized mercuric iodide material in the size range 7–52 nm. SAED results support the crystallinity of the material. In our knowledge this is the first report on the formation of nano-sized mercuric iodide by solid-gas reaction. Nanostructured materials thus obtained may improve its applications in imaging process.

Conclusions

In summary, we have synthesized mercuric iodide by solid-gas reaction using simple, inexpensive techniques for the first time. Kinetics of the reaction was studied by measuring increase in weight of the material on the micro slide (*w*) as a function of time and width of the orange red reaction product in the glass channel as a function of time. The reaction product was characterized by PXRD studies as HgI₂ with space group P4₂/nmc. Diffuse reflectance spectroscopic studies also revealed the formation of a new product. TEM and SAED results revealed the formation of nanocrystalline reaction product in the size range 7–52 nm.

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